

The Rh neutral story

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June 15, 2021

1 Intro

There are claims that people having Rh negative blood type share some physical features and have psychic abilities which are either not common or not present in people with Rh positive blood.

I am not aware of any studies trying to confirm or refute such hypothesis. Being Rh negative, I can confirm that at least some of the claims apply to me. Here, I will present my hypothesis on the origin of Rh negative blood type and other features sharing the same origin.

2 Origin

Apart from susceptibility to disease, I do not believe any major physical or psychological differences can be directly associated with blood types if these have been evolving on the same planet.

However, if two equal species are evolving on two different planets and these evolutions are separated in time, introduction of individuals from one planet to another may cause such differentiation.

After I have deduced how a creature *homo.β* is evolving into will look like, it became clear that at least some alien abduction stories are real.

I define these *aliens* as *homo.sapiens[?]* (modern man is *homo.β* and will evolve into *homo.sapiens* eventually).

Based on my theory of neurogenesis in planets, I am convinced that *homo.sapiens* performing these abductions lives (or has lived) deep below the surface of Mars.

Thus, I consider the following a plausible story:

Mars.*homo.sapiens* finds a well preserved fossil of Mars.*homo.β*, or more likely, finds a record of already sequenced genome by *homo.β* itself. Wants to revive the animal (like we would like to do with extinct species) but with no living compatible eggs on Mars, it comes to Earth.

Here, it abducts an Earth.*homo.β* female and injects the DNA of the extinct Martian *homo.β* into the egg, fertilizing it.

Martian homo. β must have been evolutionary ahead of Earth.homo. β , but let's suppose it also had an Rh negative blood (probably majority of Martian homo. β were Rh negative).

This would explain why Rh negative mothers can cause hemolytic disease in a child - if a child's blood type is separated in evolution by multiple generations it may be treated as invasive species (virus or allergen).

Coupled with the fact that immune system doesn't react to everything, this also explains why Rh negative individuals can be allergic to humanity (like I presently am[?]) - obviously, immune system associates humanity with damage.

This humanity, or human stupidity, is thus likely generally concentrated in Rh positive individuals.

Such allergic reactions may also be interpreted as evidence that Rh negative blood type has a source in effective future of Earth (past of Mars) since Rh negative blood type is present on Earth longer than global dominance and expression of humanity (damage).

If Rh negative females favor Rh negative children, obviously the advanced (more evolved) features will be more common in individuals carrying this blood type.

The abductions also explain virgin births, such as the one of Jesus.

While I was expressing cancerous personality I have often felt betrayed. Betrayed by my ex-wife, by people, industry and government.

Now, I accept my past and my future, whatever it is. Therefore, I cannot be betrayed. Whoever believes has betrayed me, sooner or later realizes it betrayed his or her self.

This is normal for every cancerous, even the ones who are to evolve into neutralum.

I, however, consider the term Rh negative inappropriate, as lack of these antigens should likely be interpreted as lack of polarization.

3 Features

I have named the introduced species homo.beta.neutralum. Due to hybridization, it may not be limited to Rh negative blood type anymore, although neutralum features should be, in any case, more common among Rh negative individuals.

Here are some of features which I believe originate in neutralum:

Feature	Notes
Preference for truth over security	Real neutralum individuals are interested in building opinions around real facts rather than manufacturing of <i>facts</i> based on opinion. Real truth seekers must have an open mind, rather than polarized one uncomfortable with big changes and thus interested in preservation of dogmas.
High intelligence	Thoughts of neutralum are neutral (objective) because proteins inside its neurons are neutral. This lack of polarization enables high intelligence. Generally, any kind of polarization leads to dependence. Entanglement with cancerous can polarize cells of neutralum which does not only decrease intelligence, but in neutralum leads to depression and can cause other diseases. Note that there is no large deviation in intelligence among the individuals of any wild species, like there is in humans and domestic animals. This strongly suggests mixing with alien species.
Introversion	Introverted intelligence is more evolved form of intelligence than extroversion. In cancerous society neutralum will always prefer to work alone and struggle to form relationships.
Retro-visions	If one is not strongly attached to current incarnation of the body it will have the ability to access memories of past incarnations stored in space of the soul. These memories can be accessed in dreams of the individual. Moments of death are most likely to be retrieved due to significant impression.
High intuition	Non-polarization allows sensitivity to smaller scale radiation which precedes events on larger scale. This enables one to sense future events.
Balance of soul and matter	The entanglement with cancerous might lead neutralum to polarize and become effectively cancerous but it will never be happy in such environment. In nature of neutralum is to strive for balance of the body of matter and the body of soul. It wouldn't be intelligent to only satisfy the needs of material body which is in time just another coat for the soul. Equally, it would not be good to sacrifice the needs of the body which evolves the space of the soul.
Interest in science, engineering Blue eye color	Without neutralums, progress in science and engineering would be extremely slow. Since variation in eye color is not variable in wild animals, it may be a feature introduced with neutralum. Originally, Earth.homo.beta may have had brown eye color. Eye colors from brown to green can be explained by variation of melanin amount in the iris. However, in blue eyes, degree of this variation is much smaller and genetically encoded, linking all blue-eyed individuals to a single ancestor[?]. This fact, coupled with the fact that blue eyes are blue due to very low melanin amount makes Mars origin likely - low melanin is expected on Mars due to larger distance from the Sun (lower insolation). All Mars.homo.beta individuals thus likely had blue eye color. Note that this suggests that some domestic animals [DNA] have also been brought from Mars and among the individuals of these species differences have to exist similar to differences between homo.beta.cancerous and homo.beta.neutralum. However, this can also be explained with soul oscillation.
Ectomorph metabolism	The ectomorphs have low fat tissue as such metabolism prefers oxidation of carbohydrates over fatty acids. Ectomorphs thus have the greatest respiratory exchange ratio (RER) and lowest oxygen uptake[?] among individuals of species. Obviously, they are adopted to low oxygen atmosphere. Such atmosphere should have existed on Mars at the time of Mars.homo.beta - larger distance from the Sun requires more CO ₂ to sustain the incubation temperature suitable for life, and higher CO ₂ implies lower atmospheric O ₂ , as evident from Earth's geological history.
Lack of Rh and possibly some other antigens	Difference in susceptibility to diseases and viruses.

Note that most of these features (except for physical ones) would evolve eventually on Earth too. Some might be evolving independently even now.

Ironically, it could be that mostly the advanced features of neutralum led to rapid development of cancerous and *premature* surface *extinction*. However I find it inappropriate to blame anyone for this - it is the cancerous who abuse this knowledge, it is neutralum who gave knowledge to someone who has not matured enough to use it responsibly and it is Mars.homo.sapiens who introduced beta.neutralum to Earth.beta.cancerous, but, at some scale, it was all written in stars already.

However, cancerous is prone to cherry-picking, so I wouldn't find it surprising if one would blame the other.

Given the fact that this is not absolute extinction but transformation, perhaps cancerous should be thankful for rapid evolution rather than blame anyone for it.

As neutralum, I feel the urge to share knowledge - it is in my nature to share it (not only it may enable better life for others, but it would be usable to me in next incarnations). Effectively, I have no choice but to do so, even though it may be abused. Everything can be abused and everything does at some point in space and time, but not at all points of space and time.

Hopefully, cancerous will grow up and develop a sense for environment before being forced to grow up.

4 Aging differences

Some people age slower than others - this is linked to metabolism, but aging is also a part of evolution.

Introduction of advanced species to less evolved environment may speed up local evolution but also suppress evolution of introduced species, leading toward synchronization - elimination of differences between indigenous and introduced species.

With upcoming neurogenesis transformation event, the pressure on synchronization should be increasing and aging differences should become more pronounced.

The rate of aging should thus be proportional to the amount of time passed since ancestor introduction.

At certain point, for individuals whose ancestors have been introduced more recently, aging may even reverse.

I believe my ancestor has been introduced here very recently, some 2000 years ago. As noticed by other people, I am aging slower than my peers. If the transfer (Judgment day) is to occur this century - as predicted, I find it likely that my aging will reverse at some point.

5 Closure

Being evolutionary ahead of homo.beta.cancerous and being a minority, obviously life on Earth for neutralum descendants is often plain suffering, as relative to neutralum, these people are savages (although the difference is decreasing over time).

There is a whole religion in homo.beta.cancerous supposedly worshiping the neutralum, but it is actually the worship of suffering of neutralum - neutralums are still discriminated, even the reincarnation of the worshiped individual.

After realizing our origins, I believe it is time for homo.beta.cancerous to acknowledge neutralum as separate species and stop expecting us to suffer for their sins.

I believe I have served my punishment, but in any case, I am done obeying the rules of cancerous and will live by instructions stored in my nature.

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